

Influence of Teachers' Academic Qualifications on the Implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Kenya: A study across Secondary Schools in Emuhaya Sub County

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ABSTRACT: Teachers undertake teacher education in their professional training and development for purposes of implementing school curriculum in their subject areas of specialization. The subject areas of specialization may be Science, humanities and language at secondary school level of education. The teacher's competence is measured in terms of academic qualification specifically, the class of degrees earned such as First Class honours; Second Class honours (Upper Division); Second Class honours (Lower Division) and Pass. Besides years of teaching and seminars attended also have value addition to their academic qualifications. In the implementation of History and Government curriculum as a subject of study at secondary school level, the teachers academic qualification helps the teacher to comprehend the objectives of the curriculum, adapting History and Government content, delivery, assessment of learning among learners and providing feedback to curriculum developers for improvement. All these activities and engagements are reflected in learners' performance. Therefore learners' performance in summative evaluation – Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examinations is used conventionally to measure the extent to which teachers' academic qualification influences the implementation of curriculum. The objective of the study was to determine the influence of teachers' academic qualifications on the implementation of History and Government curriculum in Secondary schools. A conceptual framework postulating the influence of the independent variables on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum was used to focus on the objective of the study. The findings revealed that academic qualification of a teacher accounted for 2.8% of the variation in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examinations of History and Government mean score. However the influence was not statistically significant because the p-value was 0.115 greater than the set p-value of 0.05. The findings of this study are significant to the practicing History and Government teachers and principals of secondary schools in developing strategies and methods of effective implementation of History and Government curriculum.

KEY WORDS: Emuhaya Sub County, History and Government Curriculum, Kenya: Secondary Schools, Influence, Implementation, Teachers' Academic Qualifications.

INTRODUCTION

The influence of a teacher on curriculum implementation of any discipline is multifaceted. Thus teachers thriving on their competences incorporate culturally relevant content and best practices that stimulate learners interest and participation. In every discipline teachers' endeavor to identify, prepare and utilize appropriate teaching learning resource materials and technology that enhance curricular implementation so as to meet specific learning needs. Parents are considered important stakeholders who are usually engaged to enhance curriculum implementation and share progress. Teachers on their own establish positive and inclusive classroom instructional environment that encourages learner motivation. Teachers also regularly attend seminars and workshops for professional/ career progression to stay updated with new strategies and curricular changes. Formative evaluation is undertaken to help improve learner's performance. Teachers as instructional managers enhance curriculum implementation by engaging learners actively in critical thinking which translate to better performance in summative evaluation, indicative of effective implementation of the curriculum.

Musau and Migosi (2015), in a study titled: Teachers qualification and students' academic performance in Science, Mathematics and Technology subjects in Kenya indicated that, majority of the teachers of Science Mathematics and Technological subjects were trained graduates, most of them had attended in-service courses which resulted in slight improvement in the students' performance in Science, Mathematics and Technological subjects. The study employed ex-post-facto survey research design and

simple random sampling was used to select 40 science, Mathematics and technological teachers consisting 27 men and 13 women were included, 600 students out of 3000 candidates were used. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The reviewed study focused on the teacher's qualification and student's academic performance in Science Mathematics and Technology but does not bring out how teachers qualification affects implementation of History and Government curriculum in secondary schools.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE ON INFLUENCE OF TEACHERS' ACADEMIC QUALIFICATIONS ON HISTORY AND GOVERNMENT CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION

Bonney, Amoah, Micah, Ahiamenyo, and Lemaire (2015) investigated the relationship between the quality of teachers and students' academic performance in Sekondi Takoradi Metropolitan Assembly Junior High Schools. Stratified and systematic sampling techniques were used to sample participants and the sample size was 500. Questionnaire was the main instrument used for the data collection. The results of the study showed that even though the quality of teachers was high in terms of their academic and professional qualifications, it did not reflect much in the performance of the students.

Darling-Hammond (2000), in a study titled; Teacher Quality and Students Achievement: A Review of State Policy Evidence. Critically analyzed the way in which teacher qualification and other school input were related to student's achievement across states. The study used data from a 50- state survey of policies, state case study analysis, the 1993-94 Schools, Staffing Surveys and the National Assessment of Education progress. The findings of both the qualitative and quantitative analysis suggested that policy investment in the quality of teachers may be related to improvements in students' performance. Quantitative analysis indicated that, measures of teacher preparation and certification were by far the strongest correlates of student's achievement in reading. State policy surveys and case study data are used to evaluate policies that influence the overall level of teacher qualifications within and across states. This analysis suggested that policies adopted by states regarding teacher education, licensing, hiring and professional developments may make an important difference in the qualifications and capacities that teachers bring to their work. The reviewed study indicated the way in which teacher qualification and other school input were related to student's achievement across states but does not look at how teacher qualification affects implementation of History and Government curriculum.

Khajeha, Simatwa and Baraza (2019) in a study titled: Influence of lecturer characteristics on academic achievement of engineering students in National Polytechnics in Kenya: An analytical study. The study adopted descriptive and co-relational research designs. The study population was 645 students, 41 lecturers, 2 librarians, 6 technicians and 2 principals. Simple random sampling was used to select 241 students and 37 lecturers while 1 principal, 3 technicians and 1 librarian were selected by saturated sampling. Questionnaires, interviews and document analysis guide were used to collect data. Data was analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means and regression analysis. The objective of the study was to establish the influence of lecturers' characteristics on academic achievement of students in engineering courses in National polytechnics in Kenya. The finding was that lecturers' age and experience significantly influenced academic achievement of engineering students while lecturers' qualification did not statistically influence student's academic achievement significantly. This study indicated how lecturers' characteristics influence students' academic achievement of students in engineering courses in National polytechnics in Kenya but it did not establish how teachers qualification affects implementation of History and Government curriculum in secondary schools.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework showing Influence of Teachers Academic Qualifications on the Implementation of History and Government

From Figure 1, it can be observed that teachers academic qualifications in History and Government is the sum total of the teachers performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examination university degrees, attendance and participation in seminars and workshops (capacity building) and years of experience in implementation of History and Government curriculum. All these factors are important such that being inadequate in anyone of them affects the implementation of the curriculum negatively such that teachers' academic qualification may not qualify as a significant predictor of implementation of the curriculum. Nevertheless, when all the factors are fulfilled, teachers' academic qualifications performance can be significant predictors of successful implementation of History and Government curriculum. A model therefore can be generated to explain implementation of History and Government curriculum.

Research Objective

The research objective was to establish the influence of teachers' academic qualifications on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Secondary Schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research adopted descriptive survey and correlation research designs. The target population consisted of 1 County Quality Standards Assurance Officer, 2 Curriculum Support Officers, 31 Principals, 64 History and Government teachers and 1,125 form three History and Government students totaling to 1223. The sample size consisted of 22 Principals, 2 Curriculum Support Officer, 55 History and Government teachers and 286 Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education 2020 History and Government students. Simple random sampling was used to select 55 teachers and 286 form three History and Government students. The County Quality Assurance Officer, 2 Curriculum Support Officers and 22 principals were purposively selected for the study hence 366 respondents. Data collection instruments included questionnaires, interview schedules and observations. Validity of the instruments was ascertained by three experts from the department by examining the instruments and incorporating their input. Reliability of instruments was done by piloting in 9 schools and test and re-test method was used to determine reliability where

Pearson’s (r) coefficient of 0.7 and above calculated at p- value of 0.05 was considered reliable. The reliability coefficient for teachers questionnaire was 0.78 and 0.8 for students questionnaire. Data was analyzed by use of descriptive statistics, that is, frequency counts, percentages and means. Inferential statistics, that is, regression analysis was used to determine the influence.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Category of Respondents		Frequency	Percent
Students	Male	131	45.8
	Female	155	54.2
	Total	286	100.0
Teachers	Male	22	40.0
	Female	33	60.0
	Total	55	100.0

Table 1 above illustrates that females constitute a higher percentage (54.2%) in terms of History and Government students compared to Males (45.8%). However, female (60%) teachers of History and Government constitute the majority compared to males (40%). This could have a detrimental impact on the education of male children, as there is a moderately fewer male teachers to serve as their early mentors.

Table 2: Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience in years	Frequency	Percentage
1	0	0
2	13	23.6
3	6	11
4	8	14.5
5	16	29
6	3	5.5
7	0	0
8	3	5.5
9	0	0
10	6	11
Total	55	100

From Table 2 it can be noted that majority of instructors 16 (4.7%) had a teaching experience of five years. The data exposed that a bigger percentage of teachers had an experience of five years and above hence were in a good position to answer questions regarding on the implementation of History and Government curriculum. That data also shows that no teacher had less than one year teaching experience.

Table 3: Academic Qualification of Teachers

Highest Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Bachelors of degree	55	100
Total	55	100

From Table 3, it can be noted that all the teachers had a Bachelor’s of Education degree. This depicts that the instructors engaged in the study were adequately qualified to teach and hence they were in a better position to give a comprehensive view on the status of History and Government curriculum implementation.

Table 4: Other Teaching Subjects

Subject	Frequency	Percent
Christian Religious Education	24	43.6
Geography	9	16.4
Kiswahili	22	40
Total	55	100

Table 4 reveals that majority (43.6%) of History and Government teachers taught CRE as well. It is also noteworthy that a considerable number of history and government teachers combined it with Kiswahili as well. This was important to understand other commitments of the teachers and establish whether the variation in implementation of History and Government curriculum could be accredited to the divided attention to the other subjects.

Table 5: Seminars Attended

Seminar attendance	Frequency	Percent
Termly	34	61.8
Yearly	18	32.7
Total	52	94.5

Data in Table 5 exposes that majority of the teachers (61.8%) attended seminars termly and that only a few (32.7%) attended yearly. This shows that the teachers are constantly updated on the dynamics in the history and government curriculum and thus are required to implement it smoothly. This was important to this study as it shows the progress made to ensure that the curriculum is realized. The information teachers obtain from equipped teachers with skills and knowledge that helped them to respond to questions regarding History and Government implementation.

Table 6. Students' Performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education in History and Government for the 2020 Cohort

12-Point Grade	Grade	Frequency	Percentage
1	E	0	0
2	D-	8	2.8
3	D	23	8.0
4	D+	11	3.8
5	C-	38	13.3
6	C	36	12.6
7	C+	37	13.0
8	B-	38	13.3
9	B	22	7.7
10	B+	33	11.5
11	A-	28	9.8
12	A	12	4.2
Mean Score	(7.27)		

From Table 6, majority (72.1%) of the students obtained between 6 and 12 points in History and Government in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examinations. This implies that the students' performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examinations in History and Government was generally above average. It also means that the implementation of History and Government curriculum descriptively was somewhat satisfactory.

Research Objective

The research objective was to establish the influence of teachers’ academic qualifications on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Secondary Schools.

To determine the influence of teachers’ academic qualifications on the implementation of History and Government curriculum in secondary schools, data on students’ performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education in History and Government for the 2020 cohort (Table 6) was computed and regressed against the teachers qualifications (academic, teaching experience and capacity building indices). The results were as shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Regression analysis showing the influence of Teacher Qualifications on History and Government Curriculum Implementation

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig.	F Change
1	.215 ^a	.046	.028	1.74808	.046	2.566	1	53	.115	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers’ Qualification

According to the data analysis shown in Table 7, the academic qualification of teachers did not have statistically significant influence on History and Government curriculum implementation. This is because the p-value 0.115 was greater than the set p-value of 0.05. Notwithstanding the output of these results, it can be noted that teachers qualifications accounted for 2.8% of the variations in implementation of the History and Government curriculum as signified by the Adjusted R square 0.028. Descriptively, it had been noted that most (78.1%) teachers had a teaching experience of 5 years and below. The implication of which is that, this factor may have been responsible for some ineffectiveness in curriculum implementation. Thus effectiveness in curriculum implementation improves with implementers’ experience. The more experienced the teachers’ area, the more effective they become in implementing the curriculum in any given discipline.

To confirm as to whether teacher qualifications are predictors of implementation of History and Government curriculum, ANOVA was computed and the results were as shown in Table 8.

Table 8. ANOVA Showing Influence of Teachers Qualifications on Implementation of History and Government Curriculum

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.842	1	7.842	2.566	.115 ^b
	Residual	161.956	53	3.056		
	Total	169.799	54			

a. Dependent Variable: History and Government Curriculum Implementation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teachers Academic Qualifications

From Table 8 it can be noted that teachers’ academic qualifications were not significant predictors of History and Government curriculum implementation. This was signified by the p-value which was 0.115 which was greater than the set p-value of 0.05 ($F(1, 53) = 2.566, 2 > 0.05$). This means that teachers’ qualifications cannot be relied upon to predict the successful implementation of History and Government curriculum in secondary schools. There are other factors that were not subject of the study that could be relied upon. Such factors could include learners attitude, teachers attitude, school infrastructure, school culture or ethos, teaching and learning materials, learners entry behavior (Muhando & Simatwa, 2024) and location of the schools.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data analyzed, it is clear that findings from interviews concurred with questionnaire findings as noted by Curriculum Support Officer who stated “In my honest opinion, I have never found any tangible connection between a teacher’s qualification and implementation of History and Government curriculum A teacher’s effectiveness lies on other factors such as

love for teaching, their passion and their teaching methods. Those with high qualifications and those with basic training can either perform poorly or highly depending on these factors.”

Interview findings from the County Quality Assurance Officer and the Curriculum Support Officer were in concurrence as they highlighted “the qualifications of a teacher are always expected to be a boost to a teacher’s pedagogical skills. However, in the due course, we have witnessed the contrary where teachers with lower qualifications showcase instructional prowess more than those with higher qualifications. A teacher’s ability to impart knowledge cannot be solely tied to his/her qualifications.” It has been witnessed that some teachers have high qualifications but are outshined by those with lower qualifications. Those with higher qualification or with basic education can perform better or poorly depending on their passion and love for History and Government curriculum. Nevertheless, it is important to note that qualification of a teacher may not influence his or her performance when they are considered together, however if the teachers’ qualifications were disaggregated, some notable differences could have been observed. This augment is based on the qualitative findings and students’ performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education that was generally above average on the whole.

The results concur with the findings of Khajeha, Simatwa and Baraza (2019) in a study titled: Influence of lecturer characteristics on academic achievement of engineering students in National polytechnics in Kenya: An analytical study. The study adopted descriptive and co-relational research designs. The study population was 645 students, 41 Lecturers, 2 Librarians, 6 Technicians and 2 Principals. Simple random sampling was used to select 241 students and 37 Lecturers while 1 Principal, 3 Technicians and 1 Librarian were selected by saturated sampling. Questionnaires, interviews and document analysis guide were used to collect data. Data was analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means and regression analysis. The objective of the study was to establish the influence of lecturers’ characteristics on academic achievement of students in engineering courses in National polytechnics in Kenya. The findings were that lecturers’ age and experience significantly influenced academic achievement of engineering students while lecturers’ qualification did not significantly influence students’ academic achievement. This means that lecturers’ qualifications did not significantly influence implementation of engineering curriculum in national polytechnics. It is therefore important to note that in Social Science and engineering curriculum instructors’ academic qualifications are not statistically significant. Other factors seem to be the significant drivers of curriculum implementation.

CONCLUSION

Teachers’ academic qualifications, that is their credentials in terms of degree classifications, teaching experience, in-service training and performance at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education level did not significantly influence implementation of History and Government curriculum in secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Through seminars and workshops on capacity building in implementation of History and Government curriculum:

- (i) Teachers should be encouraged to comprehend candidly the objectives of teaching History and Government in secondary schools so that they can implement the curriculum effectively and efficiently.
- (ii) Teachers should be advised on selection and implementation of appropriate teaching and learning strategies and methodologies for implementation of history and government curriculum
- (iii) Teachers should be inducted on the development of formative and summative assessments aligned to the curriculum for appropriate evaluation of learners’ for proper implementation of the curriculum.
- (iv) Team teaching should be encouraged so as to improve curriculum delivery, optimum utilization of resources, materials and technology that enhance curriculum implementation.

REFERENCES

1. Alabi, J. A. (2017). Challenges Facing Teaching and Learning of history in senior secondary schools in Ilorin west local government area, Kwara State.
2. Andrews, R, Mycock, A. & McGlynn, C. (2009). Students’ attitude towards history: does self-Identity matter? *Educational Research*. Vol. 51 (2009).

3. Batho, G. (1985). A most crucial element of curriculum: IEA guidelines for the teaching of history. In teaching of history: *Historical Association*, 42, June, 51-83
4. Bonney, E. A., Amoah, D. F., Micah, S. A., Ahiameny, C., & Lemaire, M. B. (2015). The Relationship between the Quality of Teachers and Pupils Academic Performance in the STMA Junior High Schools of the Western Region of Ghana. *Journal of Education and practice*, 6(24), 139-150.
5. Cole, R. W. (2008). *Educating Everybody's Children: Diverse Teaching Strategies for Diverse Students*, Revised and Expanded 2nd ed. Virginia: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
6. Darling Hammond, L. (2000). *Teacher Quality and Student Achievements :A Review Of State Policy Evidence*. Seattle, WA: University of Washington Centre for the Study of Teaching and Policy.
7. Jarolimek, J. (1971). *Social studies in elementary education (4th Ed.)* New York: MacMillan.
8. Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (2013). *Secondary Schools Summative Evaluation*. Nairobi: Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development
9. Kenya Institute of Education (1985). *History and Government Syllabus* .Nairobi: Kenya.
10. Khajeha, H., Simatwa, E.M.W., & Baraza, O.T. (2019). "Influence of Lecturer Characteristics on academic achievement of engineering students in National Polytechnics in Kenya. An analytical study. "*International journal of current Research*, 11, (06), 5047-5055
11. Marsh, C.J., & Willis, G. (1999). *Curriculum: Alternative Approaches, Ongoing Issues: 2nd Edition*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
12. Mezieobi, K. A. (1993). *Social studies Curriculum*. Owerri: White and White.
13. Mugenda, O.M. & Mugenda, A.G. (2003) *Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative approaches*. Nairobi: African Centre for Technical Studies press.
14. Muhando, M., & Simatwa, E.M.W. (2024) Influence of Students' Entry Behavior on History and Government Curriculum Implementation in Kenya: A Study across Secondary Schools in Emuhaya Sub County. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review* ISSN: 2581-8341 Vol. 07 Issue 12 DOI: 10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i12-49, Impact Factor: 7.943
15. Musau, L.M. & Abere, M.J. (2015).Teacher Qualification and Students' Academic Performance In Science mathematics and technology subjects in Kenya. *International Journal of Education Administration and policy states*. Vol. 7(3) 83-89
16. Mwachana, M. (2014). The Impact of History Teaching /Learning Resources on Student Performance in KCSE History Examination: A Case of Tigania and Igembe District Meru County, Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol.5 (3) 64-72.
17. Nasibi, M. (2015) A critical appraising of history taught in secondary school in Kenya. *International Journal of Academic Research In Progressive Education and Development*. Volume. 4(1) 639-654
18. Rono, D. (2016). An Assessment of the Attitude of Student Towards History and Government in Selected Secondary School in Bomet County in Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice* Vol. 7(19) 90-94.
19. Rusman, M. (2015). Curriculum Implementation at Elementary Schools :A Study on "Best Practices " Done by Elementary School Teacher in Planning ,Implementing and Evaluating the Curriculum. *Journal of Education and Practice* .Vol. 6(21) 106-112.
20. Simatwa, E.M.W., Khajeha H., & Baraza, O.T (2019). "Influence of Students Entry behavior on academic achievement in National Polytechnics in Kenya.
21. UNESCO (2013). Policy Guidelines for Mobile Learning. UNESCO.org/images/0013/001304/130432e.PDF.
22. Were, G. S. (1967). *A history of the Abaluyia of Western Kenya*. Nairobi: East African Publishing House.
23. Yeo, H. J. (2002). Teachers' perceptions of history and history teaching in secondary schools (Doctoral dissertation).
24. Zeleza, T. (1990).The Production of Historical Knowledge for schools. *Trans African Journal of History*, 19, 1-23.

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